

THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL COLLEGE EDUCATION EXPENDITURE IN ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT

Various education policies and government initiatives has been focused to improve the literacy rate of the tribal communities. After sixty- four years of independence the tribal people are still lagging behind from the development basically in the education field. Still high drop outs and illiteracy rate is high among the tribal in comparison to other communities. In recent study it has been found that there is 70.9% of the drop out among the tribal. This paper deals Illiteracy is the root cause of backwardness of the STs in Andhra Pradesh. Through various schemes and their expenditures, the government has been making serious effort for improving educational standards of them.

KEY WORDS: Tribal's, Education, Expenditure, Intermediate, College

INTRODUCTION

The tribal people in India are residing in remote areas without any direct contact with the rest of the society, without sufficient medical, proper educational facilities, without accessibility to the developmental and welfare programmes of the government. Both union and State Governments in our country have initiated so many welfare programmes for elevate tribal population in terms of education, health, employment and many more. But the condition of tribal people could not been improved. The Constitution of India laid legal provisions such as special agency courts were also set up to give speedy justice to the tribes with free of cost. However, tribal economy is intimately connected with the forests. Naturally, these communities live in wretched poverty having Spartan capital assets, health and educational facilities and scarcely safety in vagaries of nature. However, it has not managed to address the crucial issues of basic human and fundamental rights of the tribal people support the view of Herbert Spencer "Education is preparation to live completely." The Tribes Advisory Council

(TAC) was formed, consisting of political representatives and administrators, in order to advise and guide the policies of the state in relevant tribal matters. Enunciated the table Visakhapatnam, Vizianagaram and SPSR Nellore districts have 14.42, 10.05 and 9.65 percents of tribal communities out of total population. These three districts have first three tribal population districts in the state. However, Kurnool, YSR Kadapa and Krishna have last three ranks in tribal population. In present study West Godavari has 3.35 percent of tribal population; it has below in state tribal population of 5.53 percent. It can be traced the table 1.1 percent of tribal male, where as 2.78 percent of female population, it indicates the progressive gender ratio of tribal communities in Andhra Pradesh. As per 2011 census, the literacy rate among tribal communities (58.95 per cent) is found to be far below the overall literacy of the country (72.99 per cent). The female literacy rate among tribes is far lower (49.35 per cent) as compared to overall female literacy for the country (64.64 per cent). However, the significant point is the increase in total as well as female literacy among tribal community, though still at lower pace as compared to the overall population for the country. Though the tribal areas are endowed with rich natural resources the previous Government had no vision to develop the tribal areas in a comprehensive manner. The proof of this is clearly visible from the fact that the funds allotted to the tribal welfare were not spent fully. Enunciate the clearly point out that the expenditure in the last two years has improved and almost all the funds allocated are utilised compared to the previous five years where the expenditure was in the range of 50 percent to 70 percent only. The allocation under the Tribal Sub plan for the current year is 63 percent higher than the previous year and it is almost equal to the allocations under the combined state. Enunciate the table 1.3 depicts trends of total literate rate and respective tribal literacy rate from 1961 to 2011. It can be evidence from the total literacy rate increased from 28.30 to 72.99 percent, while tribal literacy rate 8.53 to 58.96 percent six decades of Indian population It reveals 157.92 percent and tribal literacy growth rate 591.21 times, it is favourable condition.¹

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A brief review is worthwhile in order to highlight what has already been depth studied in the field. In the study focussed on tribal education of Andhra Pradesh.

Gaurang Rami's (2012) paper discusses the status of primary education in the tribal district of Dang in Gujarat. In the district, there are about 412 primary schools; out of which 378 primary schools are run by the district panchayat. The paper concludes that most of the schools have buildings, but they fail to attract the girl students owing to lack of other essential amenities like drinking water as well as separate toilets for boys and girls. The common toilet facility has

prevented many tribal girls from enrolling beyond 5th standard. Hence, the drop out ratio goes higher among the tribal girls. Another problem that makes tribal students leave schools is the medium of instruction which is quite different from their own vernacular dialect.

Virginius Xaxa (2015) He says that the post Independent India also continued the same policy with little modification such as providing certain percentage of seats in state sponsored educational institutions and government services. Under these provisions, 7.5 per cent jobs were reserved both in central and state government for tribals. This has opened a large pool of government services to them. Though reservation provides employment opportunities, the lack of educational qualifications and necessary skills denied them of the jobs, and the reserved seats remain vacant in many cases. In the case of quota for higher grade services, the condition is even worse as candidates with necessary qualifications are not available.²

OBJECTIVES

- 1.To study the importance of tribal education in AP
- 2.To assess the educational monetary benefits in various educational institutions in AP

HYPOTHESES

1. To study the importance of tribal education in AP is not significant
2. To assess the educational monetary benefits in various educational institutions in AP is not significant

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The information collected in this paper is based on the secondary data by using internet, websites, magazines, books, journals, totals, averages and percentages, tables gives a qualitative approach towards this research framework.

IMPORTANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATION IN AP

The Tribal Welfare Department's mandate is to safeguard the interests of STs, guarantee rights as laid down in the Constitution, and ensure development of the tribal population through various programs and policies of the department. The department also coordinates with other departments and ministries to achieve their goals. In order to protect the economic and social interests of the tribals from industrial exploitation and to increase the pace of access to development, the department has adopted what it calls a Tribal Sub Plan Strategy since 1975. Under this plan, several programs have been introduced to bring larger sections of

the tribal population under the state's welfare programs. In addition, all other departments of the state are expected to allocate a certain percentage of their annual budgets towards development programs of scheduled tribes. Among all developmental programs, the department gives special emphasis to tribal education. In the 2009-10 annual budget, the department has proposed to allocate 79% of their budget towards education. The department believes that by giving a special impetus to education programs, which will ensure universal enrolment for primary education and provide access to tribal children to pursue higher studies in the urban areas, the socio-economic gap between tribal population and the general population can be bridged effectively. The department has made impressive strides in this direction; however, there is a need to be able to measure the progress of their programs. Measuring the performance of the Tribal Welfare Department's education programs assumes further significance given the budgetary allocation and the link education has to development of tribal communities. Thus, in the last decade there has been an attempt to streamline administrative procedures and set up systems to measure the performance of the department's programs.³

THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATION EXPENDITURE IN AP

Education is one of the most important means to improve tribal personal endowments, build capabilities, overcome constraints and in the process, enlarge available set of opportunities and choices for a sustained improvement in well-being. As per Article 45 of the Constitution of India, Universalisation of Elementary Education is a Directive Principle of State Policy that underlines the need to provide free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 years.³ In this paper an attempt is made to examine government policies for tribal education expenditure at various levels. The prominence of tribal educational school, intermediate, college expenditure in AP is shown in table-1, table-2.

TABLE-1
THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATIONAL INTERMEDIATE
EXPENDITURE IN A.P

SL.N O	SCHEME	TOTAL PROVISION	EXPENDITURE	EXPENDITURE AGAINST RS(% LAKHS)
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1	Development of Sericulture Industry in Tribal Areas	33.33	33.33	100.00%
2	Implementation of Sericulture Schemes	250	189.27	75.71%
3	others	100	35.68	35.68%
Totals		383.33	258.28	67.38%

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Annual Report 2019-20, pg.6

The table -2 reveals the development of sericulture industry in tribal areas which accounts for 94.68% it is very highly. While the Implementation of Sericulture Scheme was 87.27%. The above figures from the table clearly depicts 35.68 per cent occupying others. The prominence of tribal educational intermediate expenditure in AP shown in figure -2

FIGURE-1
THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATIONAL INTERMEDIATE
EXPENDITURE IN AP

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Annual Report 2019-20, pg.6

TABLE-2
THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATION COLLEGE EXPENDITURE IN
AP

SL. NO	Scheme	Total Provision	Expenditure	Expenditure against RS(% LAKHS)
1	Honorarium to Mentors of JKC's	0.37	0.37	100.00%
2	Rashtriya Uchcharat Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA)	1513.88	1381.88	91.28%
3	Government Degree Colleges in RIAD Areas	40	29.24	73.10%
4	Government Degree Colleges in RIAD Areas	30	19.4	64.67%
5	Rashtriya Uchcharat Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA)	3560.66	2072.83	58.21%
6	District Resource Centres	3	1.05	35.00%
7	Tribal Degree Colleges	400	94.61	23.65%
8	Welfare of Scheduled Tribes students in GDCs	26.95	0	0.00%
9	Mana TV	0.58	0	0.00%
10	Residential Degree Colleges for STs	30	0	0.00%
11	Establishment of English Language Labs	1	0	0.00%
	Total	5,606.44	3,599.38	64.20%

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Annual Report 2019-20, pg.-7

Table.3 reveals the striking feature is the dominance of the Badikostha which accounts for 100%, it is occupy the first place. The shares of percent were 91.28% %, 73.10%, 64.67%, 58.21% for Rashtriya Uchcharat Shiksha Abhiyan, Government Degree Colleges in RIAD Areas, Government Degree Colleges in RIAD Areas, Rashtriya Uchcharat Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA). While the District Resource Centres was 35.00%. The Tribal Degree Colleges was

23.65%. Other schemes percentages were not significant. The prominence of tribal education college expenditure in ap shown in figure-3

FIGURE-3

THE PERFORMANCE OF TRIBAL EDUCATION COLLEGE EXPENDITURE IN A.P

Source: Tribal Welfare Department, Annual Report 2019-20, pg.-7

RESULT

1. To study the importance of tribal education in AP is a significant
2. To assess the educational monetary benefits in various educational institutions in AP is partial significant.

CONCLUSION

Illiteracy is the root cause of backwardness of the STs in Andhra Pradesh. Through various schemes and their expenditures the government has been making serious effort for improving educational standards of them. Multiple reasons have hindered the participation of STs in education. Merely launching the schemes and their expenditures is not a panacea for evil of illiteracy among tribal masses. The benefits of these schemes have percolated to them scantily. Low level of awareness about these schemes among the tribal masses, peculiar nature of their dwellings, apathy of administrative officials in implementation of these schemes and programmes are bottlenecks in the ST's Education. Local media and ST Intelligence can work

jointly for creating awareness among the STs. The administrative machinery should be sensitized towards peculiarities of tribal habitat⁴.

REFERENCES

1. Chinnamanaidu- “dynamics of tribal education in Andhra pradesh” Jammu Research Scholar, Dept. Commerce & Business Administration Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur – 522 510. August 2018, Volume 5, Issue 8
2. Chinnamanaidu-opcit, Pg.no.153
3. Bella Vista, Raj Bhavan Road, Khairatabad, Administrative Staff College of India, Hyderabad 500082, India harish@asci.org.in Phone: 91-40-66534284, Mobile: 91-9849427474 <http://www.asci.org.in> | Page 2
4. Dr A. Punnaiah-“ issues and challenges of tribal education: a study of telangana state” Vol 4, No 1 (2018), pg .1
5. Tribal Welfare Department, Annual Report 2019-20, pp-5to 7.